

→ [MIMS: Technology as the 0th Domain](#) ¹

MESS 0027

MIMS 2.62 - The Four Domains to win WW3.0 and avoid World War III²

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the author puts forth a reason and schema for winning the four non-conventional domains of war (in the 7-domain array: 7DA) in order to *avoid a deadly, genocidal conventional world war and civil war*. Therefore the author puts forth what Sun Tzu willed: design a military not merely for capacity to inflict death and destruction, but to win without fighting. To a) attack by stratagem and b) take entire regions without fighting, we want to find avenues to at least defend ourselves, and our liberal way of life (tolerance, if not acceptance)... without firing a shot. If that can be done, perhaps - just perhaps, and narrowly - we can avoid World War III.

Keywords: Economics - Technology - Cyberspace - Outer Space - World War 3.0 - Domains of War - POS

¹ https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain

² MIMS 2.85

Introduction

World War 3.0, as explained elsewhere is a hyperdimensional, asymmetric, multi-layer, multi-phase field-game, of affectation, influence, and pressure application. It is “won” online, in political arenas, in the media, school boards, courts, and the floors of Congress. In a lot of ways, whoever pays the most, wins, and when they win, then they can move. Ideally: without a shot fired. The NWO *had* basically won the board without a shot fired, but the New Axis has “struck back” at the USA ® Empire (or NATO), in its own way in 2022, putting the real America, and Americans, their allies in NATO, and sympathizers worldwide in a strange, and awkward position financially and referentially.³ Financially, the SWIFT banking system has more or less failed⁴ as liberalism, and more specifically neoliberalism and neoconservatism has failed. More poignantly, they lost their central power over China and Russia⁵, who plan to use gold as a backing system for their own morbid economies. Only time will tell if the Keynesians⁶ are more right than the gold-backers. The marketing for both is about as convincing as the idea that cryptocurrencies are a good hedge against the fiat money system, at least post ETH/proof of stake⁷. That is to say: not at all convincing.

However, the basic inflation of the proposed dæther through Big Data and Quantitative Easing has presented now a new issue: who can take the lead in a post-COVID world? The NWO is fractured... the Deep State is running amok, the NGOs like the World Economic Forum⁸ suddenly have more power⁹ than anyone intended and the rebellion against corporate wokeism is more expensive than Disney¹⁰, Netflix¹¹, Facebook¹², or any other conglomerate expected.¹³ Already, calls for more patriotism, family values, increased birth rates, and the dialing back of social Marxism are underway.¹⁴ In short: WW3.0 is becoming a “you-know-what-show.” Right now, it is not China’s game to lose, it is anyone’s to win: Brazil, India, even the pathetic and bruised European Union are now also in the running to take the lead position for the “Royal Sway” as the ancients called it. It is not even clear that a post-Trump America can keep the RS, even with force.

It is with this issue in mind - and the future of six continents and almost 8 billion lives - that we must think about what strategies are vital for the continuing success of a peaceful, and (until recently¹⁵) liberalizing world. Of course we do not mean liberal in terms of American politics, but in terms of un-monarchical freedom. Freedom from tyranny, communism, socialism, oligarchy, and many other forms of dictatorship.

Of the 7-Domain Array

Excluding Language, in our future discussion of the 8-Domain Array¹⁶, we are primarily intrigued in this document with the 7 domains of war that preoccupy the Pentagon. Of these, three are traditional, the 0th (1st one) is common to any domain of human development, and the other three are the domains of the new

³ <https://www.dlapiper.com/fr/france/insights/publications/2022/03/explaining-swift-and-recent-actions/>

⁴ <https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/swift-primer-west-moves-freeze-russia-out-international-payments-2022-02-26/>

⁵ Who now have a gold-backed financial system; rather than backed by fiat dæthereal magik.

⁶ <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/2014/09/basics.htm>

⁷ MESS0034: POS x MIMS 2.6X - the Proof of Stake POS Wave; retractions, failures, and lessons learned

⁸ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/w/world-economic-forum.asp>

⁹ The support from Black Rock, Inc. <https://www.weforum.org/organizations/blackrock-inc>

¹⁰ <https://www.fool.com/investing/2022/10/20/why-is-disney-stock-down-37-this-year/>

¹¹ <https://www.cnn.com/2022/07/19/media/netflix-earnings/index.html>

¹² <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2022/10/26/facebook-meta-earnings-report/>

¹³ That’s why FREETH is better than ESG! www.freeth.us

¹⁴ Why Companies Went Woke — It’s Not What You Think | Vivek Ramaswamy | POLITICS | Rubin Report

¹⁵ 2018-current

¹⁶ MIMS 2.801 - MESS0037: the Eight Domain Array - badge and meaning

asymmetric war arena. In “Unrestricted Warfare,”¹⁷ the concept is put forth that in the new era, there is no limit or place to not participate. So Lawfare, for example, has a ratio of components that are primarily economic, partially digital (cyberspace), and are fought in *other* lands. Meanwhile, economic warfare, such as stock market fake IPOs¹⁸ to rob cash, and steal IP¹⁹, are fought in cyberspace, and through control of information in the air and space (satellites), to obfuscate the reality on the ground of Chinese businesses. Etc.

Briefly, we will describe the conditions which are concerning, and what must be observed, about each of the four domains that concern us in World War 3.0. The sum total of them resulting in a labyrinthian pathway that leads to the Total Shi (TS). If that TS is *perceived* as being favorable to either side, and the threat of Mutually Assured Destruction (MAD) is *also* minimized, then it is expected that the war will move into the traditional SEAL domains - Sea, Land, Air.

Technology

Because the advancement of technology, itself a MIMS which enables perpetual *futurization* and, more importantly or as importantly: bootstraps itself regardless of scientific momentum, provides a foundation throughout all the war domains, it is URGENT to control this bottleneck. There are three key reasons... the BCS system... why we must conquer and continue to hold the 0th Domain, just in activating the facet of MilDef²⁰:

1. **Bottlenecks** - the control of the logistics, through ORDA, of the bottleneck determines routes of supply and reinforcement.
2. **Chokepoints** - the deadly terrain of “narrow defiles” is a physical example, while lifelines and ammunition supplies are more temporary; however without control of our own chokepoint, the strategic adversary has the ability to **throttle** our life support and security, to suit their whims and needs.
3. **Shatterpoints/Shining Points** - looking at where systems break down, and determining precisely the location (where) to strike, we must also be cognizant of the remaining dimensions, particularly the when. Intuitive knowledge from our minds will often help us to see the where, when it “shines” to us.

When it comes to technology there are more options than ever. But which ones create alignment within our positional Shi²¹ and match our innate Shi²², and would help us disrupt the momentum of the adversary? I suspect that out of all contracts, 95% of them are essentially worthless for the present moment of alignment, based on our own BCS. More work is needed to find algorithmic approximation and precision for the BCS before a concise method of evaluating products and technology is possible.

Outer Space

In terms of the “high ground” there is no higher ‘ground’ than Outer Space. However, it is unreasonable to assume the Earth can be reasonably directed or protected in certain ranges from certain altitudes. There are, therefore, key “heights” to consider where dynamic protection might be had, and create many job opportunities. Obviously these will come at different SPACER²³ stages, and those are provided:

¹⁷ <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>

¹⁸ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt7215388/>

¹⁹ www.cbsnews.com/news/chinese-hackers-took-trillions-in-intellectual-property-from-about-30-multinational-companies/

²⁰ Military Defense

²¹ *le* - field or scalar array

²² *le* - numerical value

²³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

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- Below Sea Level
 - Deep Mining Phase 2→3, Stage 1
 - Deep Ocean cities Phase 3, Stage 1
 - Surface
 - Earth Kinetic Defense system Phase 2, Stage 1
 - Spaceport City mutual AI defense system Phase 3, Stage 1
 - Thermosphere
 - Birkeland Polyphase Superweb 0th version (R&D) Phase 2→3, Stage 1
 - Ion Cannon Phase 3, Stage 1
 - Moon
 - Moonport/base Phase 1, Stage 2
 - BPS v0.5 Phase 2→3, Stage 2
 - Mars
 - Mars base Phase 1, Stage 3
 - Mars Cities & Terraforming Phase 2→3, Stage 3
 - Venus→Mars CO₂ transfer (atmosphere mining) All of Stage 3→5
 - Venus
 - Venus terraformation Stage 4→5
 - Earth→Mars Dual Layer Plasma Defense System Phase 2, Stage 1→Stage 4
 - Jupiter
 - BPS v1 Stage 5
 - Asteroid Mining & Kinetic Defense System v3 Stage 3 & 4→Stage6
 - TNS²⁴
 - Solar System Defense Bases and Force Stages 8→10+

It is clear that the MilDef pole of the present US Military Empire²⁵ (and NATO) will be able to find ways and means to fill in the gaps. So long as these do not threaten the viability of an economic buffer and self-regulating system, then there won't be an issue of developing more military power. When these powers grow, then there is a threat of in-fighting on the planet (more than normal). That will simply not work for our long term survival. It isn't wise, or sustainable, without sending mankind back to the woods.

Cyber Space

The digital Information Age is perhaps a source of data advantage, or perhaps a deatheric²⁶ powerhouse of metaphysics. All that matters is that the leading edge of Internet-related technology and research is as much of a hook of motivation as money; and they seem related. More to the point, it is technology related and dependent. But actually the main, main point is that cyberspace is where the forefront of IQ and TIQ²⁷ assets are being applied daily, and in pursuit often of real motion of the TS. Those countries with the top and most hackers, tools, and hardware, with good network controls and various advantages (like quantum or supercomputers, AI, etc.) will win the race. This is, in the author's opinion, self-evident.

What isn't evident to most contemporaries of technology, engineering, and warfare is that there are other influential factors and side topics related:

²⁴ Trans Neptunian System

²⁵ <https://bit.ly/3SS7jZ3>

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

²⁷ Technical Intelligence Quotient - as an asset. ^

- Database control and quality
- Data integrity
- Memory Protection and Security
- Cybersecurity, etc.
- Dark Web spaces and similar apps (Secret social media)
- Decentralized Internet & Finance
- The Gestalt and Zeitgeist of the World Wide Web
- The Collective
- Optics and “the narrative”
- Computational speed vs. workpower (FLOPs)
- Workflow (both use and improvement, ie: efficiency)
- Martiality; as in literal military or weaponized use (including cyberbullying)
- Etc.

The part that isn't evident is how these directly, tangentially, or indirectly influence the TS of larger physical structures, including business/corporations, governments, military branches, NGOs, social groups, culture, and technological evolution itself. The desire to create a message that goes viral, for instance, has direct implications in Psychological Operations²⁸, in conventional²⁹, or asymmetric³⁰ (perhaps guerilla³¹) warfare. Obviously this influence is primarily through propaganda control³². But it can be as direct in weaponization (such as doxxing), sabotage (hacking), campaigning, and infrastructural attack (various).

Economics

The most pertinent infrastructure attacks are related to utilities, energy grid, traffic systems, airports, trains, etc. But also, these are economic, and in fact the attack of banking and stock markets et al. will constitute a real and grave threat to the Allies. This is well known, from mass government level to smaller terrorist attacks, such as the stock market attack portrayed in “Dark Knight Rises.”

Figure 1 - Bane takes over Gotham Stock Exchange with force in order to make trades to wreck Wayne Enterprises; ([gif](#)) credit: Warner Bros/makeagif.com

The ability of bad actors and strategic adversaries to wreak havoc upon our infrastructure, especially coupled with simultaneous physical infrastructure attack (bombs, drone-grenades etc.) is something that requires low discipline *and* is highly probable. Suicide bombing the Boston Marathon³³, ultimately, was a pointless and mindless tactical loss for the Jihadis. But a seriously strategic maneuver against the economy would be devastating to many more; perhaps billions. The author is

²⁸ <https://irp.fas.org/doddir/army/fm3-05-30.pdf>

²⁹ <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA302389.pdf>

³⁰ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317509465_Asymmetric_Warfare_and_Psyops

³¹ <https://cryptome.org/2012/05/cia-guerilla-psyops.pdf>

³² [MESS0034: POS x MIMS 2.6X - the Proof of Stake POS Wave; retractions, failures, and lessons learned](#)

³³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boston_Marathon_bombing

going to refrain from teaching the ways, on account of national security, and really, just compassion for civilians, etc. However, suffice it to say a three-prong attack (and therefore defense prepared for a repelling of said attacks) would include:

1. Digital Software infrastructure
2. Outer Space hardware
3. Surface Infrastructure, related to electrifying the markets themselves, computer distribution centers, etc.

And in that order.

The Ever-Blossoming Strategy

What limits most generals and strategists, cannot be allowed to limit the jueshi³⁴ (爵士 knights) or you shui (遊說 lobbyists) in their application of control of the Shi 勢^{35, 36}. Also, they must force the enemy's Shi 勢^{37, 38} to be limited while theirs expands. In almost every case of campaigning, including Russia's recent debacle in the Ukraine, the positional advantage, strategic configuration, or power position - the Momentum - is limited rate. These limits are definitely defined, and probably predictable. Hitler actually thought he could keep rolling up all of Europe and Russia, while fighting the USA... only with tanks and airplanes (and bombs). It was foolish and absolutely ridiculous. But that level of tomfoolery in the hands of a single person is dangerous. The more powerful thing, though, is a superstructure that can leverage various parts of itself, at different moments of pre-engineered time (only possible if one knows the Changes), to attack the Shi³⁹ anywhere, anytime.

Therefore let us think about one, or two, ways that this can be enacted; mostly to see how we can deconstruct the fascists, oligarchy, and neo-feudal pædo-elite and prevent them from having the Superpower Superposition⁴⁰. It was dangerous when the Bildeburger/Bohemian Grove types, all subservient to the Trilateral Commission etc., were able to maximize their financial control (via the Military Industrial Complex) of the US Military... to control the Superposition. Imagine now, 50 years later, with the use of the FAANG and Big Data, that they gained this level of power. They cannot be allowed to. It is very important that the common People, and those scientists who are aligned not to Scientism, or to Big Data/Pharma, etc. come together to *rate limit* the "they." But... nevertheless... the American Military structure needs this strategy now that the [stupid/short-sighted, or insnae] NGOs and secret societies have *juiced up* the Chinese military superstructure via the CCP (now Chussia/New Axis).

"Observe calmly; secure our position; cope with affairs calmly; hide our capacities and bide our time; be good at maintaining a low profile; and never claim leadership." – Deng Xiaoping's "24 Character Strategy

³⁴ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23351455>

³⁵

https://www.esd.whs.mil/Portals/54/Documents/FOID/Reading%20Room/Litigation_Release/Litigation%20Release%20-%20China's%20Perception%20of%20Strategic%20Advantages%20of%20First%20Strike,%20Preemption,%20and%20Preventive%20Wars%20%20201406.pdf

³⁶ https://carnegieendowment.org/files/Tellis_Blackwill.pdf

³⁷ <https://nuke.fas.org/guide/china/dod-2007.pdf>

³⁸ <http://sun-tzu-aow.blogspot.com/2009/05/chapter-5-strategic-military-power.html>

³⁹

https://www.academia.edu/36282136/How_Translators_Choose_to_Render_Sun_Tzus_Meaning_of_sh%C3%AC_%E5%8B%A2_in_The_Art_of_War

⁴⁰ The black SS in MESS is for Strategy Series; however the SS here we will say is the *true* black SS. Note the SS throughout the paper: Solar System - Secret Social - Shatter-Shining Points - Secret Societies

Electrical Unrestricted Warfare

The key - fortunately or unfortunately - to all of this is the source of energy... of electricity... that will power it. For example, Bitcoin was a MIMS, but after tinkering by the major power, multiple anti-MIMS have been created which the author will expose in a future MESSy. Primarily through China's digital-yuan, Britcoin, and the new ETH based on Proof of Stake, which is more energy efficient (for them), and less helpful to the world in converting the Force to currency (\$\$). But in the end, inverting the *cares* for the People gives the powerful governments more power.

How the military pays attention to this issue is really a matter of delicacy. If you attend the same barbecues and your daughter goes to the same private schools as the POS's,^{41 42} it is hard to get a sense of *when* to take that hard line, which defines protecting one's nation and drawing it. The Spanish didn't kick the Moors out for 700 years.⁴³ The Chinese didn't root out the "foreign devils" until the mid-20th Century... and then they invited bad German philosophy instead. It's difficult to remove bad programs. People will say they are patriotic, or love their families and parents, etc. but do they *really*? Will they go the extra mile for their country? JFK asked us too, and he was assassinated by the CIA via George Hickey.⁴⁴ We do not know the reasons, particularly, but we know that "they" were not happy for JFK to print silver dollars⁴⁵ or talking about the Secret Societies⁴⁶. Were these SS in league with Ike's "Military Industrial Complex"⁴⁷? Or, rather, were they co-opting the patriots within the Pentagon/CENTCOM etc., as the author suspects?

Either way, General Milley did treason in 2020, and went unpunished.⁴⁸ Not just unpunished: he was rewarded. It is patently insane for a general of any rank, let alone *that* rank, to call our strategic adversary (China) and say he would warn them if we attacked... because China would definitely not do the same. It's just faulty *thinking* if one can call it that. So will the entire MIC, or at least the Pentagon or the JSOC teams, etc. really fight for the country? Unknown. But the war is declared (by Chussia), and the *elite* - and NATO - certainly want to egg it on⁴⁹. So we must, in a matter of defense (whether we be righteous, or self-righteous cowards) establish global electrical superiority in terms of TS. And right now, we are behind⁵⁰. We are behind because China embraces the PEMF and SPACERS revolution, and are building plasma fusion⁵¹ and thorium fission reactors.⁵² They *will* build the Vajra (PTG⁵³) making machines the author predicts, among other things, within

⁴¹ [MESS0006: POS Theory Grows Because Agenda](#)

⁴² [MESS0013: the POS and Change crossing](#)

⁴³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reconquista>

⁴⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Mortal-Error-Shot-That-Killed/dp/149095242X>

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Executive_Order_11110

⁴⁶ [John F Kennedy talking about secret society](#)

⁴⁷ <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/president-dwight-d-eisenhowers-farewell-address>

⁴⁸

<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/katiepavlich/2021/09/14/new-reporting-shows-general-milley-engaged-in-a-coup-against-trump-n2595858>

⁴⁹ <https://21stcenturywire.com/2022/05/04/carlson-heres-why-the-democrats-are-taking-us-to-war-with-russia/>

⁵⁰ If we aren't lying, saying we are when really we are ahead; which is great Art of War. The author hopes this is the true situation, and fears the honesty of our military in that it *really is behind*. But with the greed, it's hard to tell.

⁵¹ <https://www.livescience.com/chinas-1-trillion-artificial-sun-fusion-reactor-just-got-five-times-hotter-than-the-sun>

⁵²

<https://www.france24.com/en/asia-pacific/20210912-why-china-is-developing-a-game-changing-thorium-fuelled-nuclear-reactor>

⁵³ Perattian Thunderbolt Generator

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_Location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

the inside of Stage 1 of Phase 1, as they move to conquer the Moon and Thermosphere in Stage 2 (and Beyond.)

Once this occurs - once TGE is conquered⁵⁴ - then all bets are off as to who can ever challenge the holder of this Shi. BUT they will be capable, if programmed (with the right FSAI and TAI), and pre-engineered properly, to create a *Laputa*⁵⁵ like Superpositioned Superpower that is unchallengeable and ruthless. It will *not* be liberal, and it will be neither right nor left, nor humane. It will be about profit, production, materialism, consumption, and soul-crushing power for power's sake.

For this reason, among all reasons, that barring Jesus and the angels of Valhala come through the veil and crush the human and dæmonic forces⁵⁶, the US Military can and must develop the ever-blossoming strategy, via both energetico-electric dominance (not control, nor mere guidance), and S.C.A.L.E.!

At such a point the USM and CENTCOM can protect what matters most to the author and to Americans in every country (citizen or no): liberty, the *Pursuit*⁵⁷, and children. Without this, if the *lever handle* falls into the wrong hands... it will be an era of Dark AI dominated darkness, depression, and destruction. We will not make it to Stage 3 of Phase 1, and therefore will not survive the next Cat-7 catastrophe, or alien invasion, whichever comes first.

It's a Problem of S.C.A.L.E.

AIM™ is about scalability, repeatability, and scriptability; however in the context of the 7DA, we will focus on this acronym:

Security	Command	Attitude	Lubrication	Energetics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Digital ➤ Economic ➤ Stock Market ➤ Banking System ➤ Monetary ➤ Minerals ➤ Arable Land ➤ Coasts ➤ Industrial Centers ➤ Highways & Bridges ➤ Hospitals ➤ Bases & ranges ➤ Airports ➤ Water Treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ De-Fi like CENTCOM ❖ FSAI v TAI ❖ Overrides (manual and auto) ❖ Data prediction ❖ Terrain Selection ❖ Territory etc. ❖ Resolution ❖ Manpower ❖ Industrial Rate ❖ Mineral Supply ❖ Oil & gas ❖ Education re-tool ❖ TIQ Assets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Can do, will do ➤ Do it right ➤ Do it for the right reasons ➤ Genuine ➤ Loyalty & Honor ➤ Power share ➤ Equality of Opp... not "equity" ➤ Individual Justice ➤ Pay it Forward ➤ "Grandchildren's Grandchildren" ➤ Nothing for free ➤ Country First 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Get out of the way⁵⁸ ❖ Deregulate on tax & finance end ❖ Regulate the government's regulations ❖ Military: obey the Chain of Comm. ❖ Less lube on Intel - protect Freedom ❖ More lube on finding Pedos ❖ Stop the HFI⁵⁹ ❖ Industrial Accel. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Control the sources of energy ➤ Dominate the energy industries ➤ Keep power out of the hands of Big Oil & Tech ➤ Exploit Space Energy & all TGE ➤ Promote healthy kids and society ➤ Promote the Correct Flow ➤ Have a real reason to fight.

⁵⁴ Fusion, clean fission, true solar, sound/cymatics, geothermal, Stirling/Gradient, ambient and radiant energy (ARE), plasma + Birkeland Currents, radio recapture, scalar, æther, and counterspatial (0-point)

⁵⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Castle_in_the_Sky

⁵⁶ <https://bit.ly/3fnjnUA>

⁵⁷ Happiness, Property, and A More Perfect Union.

⁵⁸ If it's wrong: get in the way!

⁵⁹ Human Flesh Industry

The only way to scale is to deal with the things that are blocking it. The S.C.A.L.E. system of understanding will, as far as the military can (not being Congress), promote a society that promotes good and healthy recruits, and a homeland worth defending. That creates a high morale, and a high propensity for creating a People that stand for their neighbors, their country, and loving not just God, but all people. Not their sins. Not their philosophies. But their original selves, as humans of the human race.

The defeat of the P.O.S. that want to undermine our countries, our West, in order to gain power for themselves (especially NGOs and Trashademia) or for their secret (financier) allies, members of the New Axis... depends not upon guns, missiles, and bombs. It depends on weaponizing TIQ, IQ, and even EQ to defeat propagandists, hackers, and enemy-combatant scientists. There *are* enemy-combatant scientists, and the fact that NASA scientists were teaching rooms full of them on how to make hypersonic missiles is as much or more a part of the problem as the sex slave money in the Human Flesh Industry, or the Big Pharma/Chem-food oligarchy. Either way: manpower decreases as you rob children's lives, dreams, and futures... and ultimately keep the best of the best out of the US Military. This is part of their asymmetric attack, and therefore, it's important to deal with *before* we are able to actually scale the SPACERS movement, and to build these kinds of electrical and energetic systems which grow Human Energy & Momentum⁶⁰.

⁶⁰ <https://teslauniverse.com/nikola-tesla/articles/problem-increasing-human-energy>

References

1. "MIMS: Technology as the 0th Domain," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://bit.ly/3G6s2D1>
2. "Technology as the 0th War Domain," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain
3. MIMS 2.85
4. "SWIFT and the Ukraine conflict: Latest developments," DLA Piper, M. McKee & C. Whittaker, 2022, <https://www.dlapiper.com/fr/france/insights/publications/2022/03/explaining-swift-and-recent-actions/>
5. "Explainer: What is SWIFT and how will its removals impact Russia?" Reuters, T. Bergin, 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/swift-primer-west-moves-freeze-russia-out-international-payments-2022-02-26/>
6. "What Is Keynesian Economics?" International Monetary Fund, S. Jahan, A. S. Mahmud, & C. Papageorgiou, 2014, <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/2014/09/basics.htm>
7. "MESS0034: POS x MIMS 2.6X - the Proof of Stake POS Wave; retractions, failures, and lessons learned," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, Coming Soon
8. "World Economic Forum (WEF): Definition and History of Meeting," Investopedia, J. Kagan, 2022, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/w/world-economic-forum.asp>
9. "BlackRock," World Economic Forum, L. D. Fink, 2022, <https://www.weforum.org/organizations/blackrock-inc>
10. "Why Is Disney Stock Down 37% This Year?" The Motley Fool, D. Cook, 2022, <https://www.fool.com/investing/2022/10/20/why-is-disney-stock-down-37-this-year/>
11. "Netflix loses subscribers, but stops the bleeding," CNN Business, F. Pallotta, 2022, <https://www.cnn.com/2022/07/19/media/netflix-earnings/index.html>
12. "Meta's Zuckerberg sounds positive note on metaverse bet amid revenue decline," The Washington Post, N. Nix, 2022, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2022/10/26/facebook-meta-earnings-report/>
13. "F.R.E.E.T.H. Score," Sf. R. Careaga, <https://sites.google.com/view/star-enterprises-intrasite/spacers/reeth>
14. "Why Companies Went Woke — It's Not What You Think," Youtube/The Rubin Report, V. Ramaswamy, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-WAs7J8emc4>
15. "MIMS 2.801 - MESS0037: the Eight Domain Array - badge and meaning," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, Coming Soon
16. "Unrestricted Warfare," Beijing: PLA Literature and Arts Publishing House, Q. Liang & W. Xiangsui, 1999, <https://www.c4i.org/unrestricted.pdf>
17. "The China Hustle," IMDb, J. Rothstein, 2018, <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt7215388/>
18. "Chinese hackers took trillions in intellectual property from about 30 multinational companies," CBS News, N. Sganga, 2022, <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/chinese-hackers-took-trillions-in-intellectual-property-from-about-30-multinational-companies/>
19. "SPACERS," (EPEMC) Gateway. Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers?a_uthuser=0
20. "US Military Footprint," Sf. R. Careaga, <https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/viewer?hl=en&ll=5.372319691034644%2C0&z=2&mid=1yRfhlCowF3RgTw20k2cwjvVbVXWOB0eG>
21. "MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether
22. "Psychological Operations," Headquarters, Department of the Army, 2005, <https://irp.fas.org/doddir/army/fm3-05-30.pdf>
23. "An Overview of Psychological Operations (PSYOP)," Library of Congress, Prepared by Analyst G. Curtis, 1989, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA302389.pdf>
24. "Asymmetric Warfare and Psyops," ResearchGate, C. Malin et al, 2017, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317509465_Asymmetric_Warfare_and_Psyops
25. "Psychological Operations in Guerrilla Warfare," Tayacan, estimated pub date- 2012, <https://cryptome.org/2012/05/cia-guerilla-psyops.pdf>
26. "Boston Marathon bombing," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boston_Marathon_bombing
27. "Disputation in Ancient Chinese Culture: Early China," Jstor/Cambridge University Press, J. L. Kroll, 1985-1987, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23351455>
28. "China's Perception of the Strategic Advantages of First Strike, Preemption, and Preventative Wars Report," Thayer Limited, LLC, Submitted to Pentagon, 2014, https://www.esd.whs.mil/Portals/54/Documents/FOID/Reading%20Room/Litigation_Release/Litigation%20Release%20-%20China%27s%20Perception%20of%20Strategic%20Advantages%20of%20First%20Strike.%20Preemption.%20and%20Preventive%20Wars%20%20201406.pdf
29. "Revising U.S. Grand Strategy Toward China," Council on Foreign Relations, Council Special Report No. 72, R. D. Blackwill & A.J. Tellis, 2015, https://carnegieendowment.org/files/Tellis_Blackwill.pdf
30. "Annual Report to Congress: Military Power of the People's Republic of China, Office of the Secretary of Defense, 2007, <https://nuke.fas.org/guide/china/dod-2007.pdf>
31. "Art of war, Chapter 5: Strategic Military Power," Sun Tzu, 2009, <http://sun-tzu-aow.blogspot.com/2009/05/chapter-5-strategic-military-power.html>
32. "How Translators Choose to Render Sun Tzu's Meaning of shì (勢) in The Art of War," Academia, J. F. Sullivan, https://www.academia.edu/36282136/How_Translators_Choose_to_Render_Sun_Tzus_Meaning_of_sh%C3%AC_%E5%8B%A2_in_The_Art_of_War
33. "MIMS 2.83 - POS Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory
34. "MESS0013 - The crossing of POS Theory and time as a subset of Change Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87898394/MESS0013_The_crossing_of_POS_Theory_and_time_as_a_subset_of_Change_Theory

35. "Reconquista," Wikipedia,
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reconquista>
36. "Mortal Error: The Shot That Killed JFK," Amazon, B. Menninger, 2013,
<https://www.amazon.com/Mortal-Error-Shot-That-Killed/dp/149095242X>
37. "Executive Order 11110," Wikipedia,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Executive_Order_11110
38. "John F Kennedy talking about secret society," Youtube, M. Aidan, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wSyJaUxwP-E>
39. "President Dwight D. Eisenhower's Farewell Address," The U.S. National Archives and Records Administration, 1961,
<https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/president-dwight-d-eisenhowers-farewell-address>
40. "New Reporting Shows General Milley Committed Treason," Townhall.com, K. Pavlich, 2021,
<https://townhall.com/tipsheet/katiepavlich/2021/09/14/new-reporting-shows-general-milley-engaged-in-a-coup-against-trump-n2595858>
41. "Carlson: 'Here's Why the Democrats Are Taking Us to War With Russia'" 21st Centurywire.com, 2022,
<https://21stcenturywire.com/2022/05/04/carlson-heres-why-the-democrats-are-taking-us-to-war-with-russia/>
42. "China's \$1 trillion 'artificial sun' fusion reactor just got five times hotter than the sun," Livescience.com, B. Turner, 2022,
<https://www.livescience.com/chinas-1-trillion-artificial-sun-fusion-reactor-just-got-five-times-hotter-than-the-sun>
43. "Why China is developing a game-changing thorium-fuelled nuclear reactor," France24.com, S. Seibt, 2021,
<https://www.france24.com/en/asia-pacific/20210912-why-china-is-developing-a-game-changing-thorium-fuelled-nuclear-reactor>
44. "Proposed Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location in Versailles, KY Comparison of Predicted Models and LiDAR scans of Big Sink location in Woodford County; Addendum for Plasmaglyphs and the Megafauna Extinction," ResearchGate, 2019,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph
45. "Castle in the Sky," Wikipedia,
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Castle_in_the_Sky
46. "If I were the Aliens," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
<https://bit.ly/3z0RE19>
47. "The Problem of Increasing Human Energy," The Century Magazine, N. Tesla, 1900,
<https://teslauniverse.com/nikola-tesla/articles/problem-increasing-human-energy>